

The Influencing Factors and Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Job Performance of Primary and Junior Secondary School Teachers: Empirical Study Based on Mali's Bamako and Kita Regions

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Abstract:

Over decades, Malian primary and junior secondary school teachers have gone through work stoppages, strikes, and demonstrations claiming better living and working conditions. These incessant claims have caused the loss of much learning and teaching time and are charged being one of the causes of students' failure. This study examines the factors influencing Malian primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction and establishes the correlations between their job satisfaction and job performance. We used a sequential explanatory mixed-methods design to examine the factors influencing Malian primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction. The quantitative phase consisted of five hundred and twenty (n=520) teachers selected using stratified

random sampling techniques. In contrast, the qualitative phase consisted of twenty (n=20) participants purposively selected from the quantitative phase based on their level of dissatisfaction. SPSS software was used to analyze the data. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data collected from the interviews. Overall, the findings showed that most of the teachers (51 %) were not satisfied with their job. The study showed that urban teachers are more satisfied with their job than rural teachers. A significant correlation was found between teachers' general level of satisfaction and their job performance. It showed that the more satisfied teachers are, the better students' academic performance in Mali.

Keywords: *Mali, job satisfaction, job performance, teachers, relationship.*

Introduction

Ainley and Carstens, (2018) define teachers' job satisfaction as the sense of fulfillment and gratification that teachers experience through their work as a teacher. It is a combination of positive and negative appraisals teachers make about the teaching profession (Skaalvik &

Skaalvik, 2015). From these definitions, we observe that teachers' emotional state and appreciation toward their jobs are essential for the quality of teaching and learning delivery service. There is an increasing consensus that highly qualified and effective teachers are necessary to improve students' performance

(Little et al., 2009). Several studies conducted on teachers' job satisfaction have concluded that a good and quality education cannot be achieved without well committed and dedicated teachers in their careers (Ansah-Hughes, 2016). Thus effectual functioning of any educational institution depends on teachers' professional commitment. Having stimulated teachers is one of the indispensable preconditions of a successful educational system in which students from different backgrounds can prosper and reach their full potential (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2021).

Adversely, teacher dissatisfaction negatively affects students learning and the productivity of schools since teachers have more effect on student learning than any other factor (Opper, 2019). There is a positive relationship that is stable from year to year between the quality of teachers and student gains in learning and is considered central in promoting students' achievement (Atkinson et al., 2010). However, the decline in job satisfaction reduces the teacher's self-efficacy to meet students' needs and psychological disorders, leading to absenteeism and a high level of claims (Troman & Woods, 2000).

Interestingly, teachers are often pointed to as the problem when learning fails to materialize because of their fundamental role in the learning process. In low-income countries, plenty of children still lacks essential reading and numeracy skills when they complete primary school (Bold et al., 2017). Improving teacher quality has been identified as the key to tackling this global learning crisis

Despite the great importance of teachers in nation development, Mali, like other sub-Saharan African countries, in 1985 under the press of the World Bank and (International Monetary Funds (IMF), has proceeded with a structural adjustment program that advocated downsizing the numbers of civil servants, including teachers (Ali, 2009). This situation has led to a teacher shortage, low salary pays, and an economic crisis. The lowly unmotivated and unsatisfied teachers in the teaching services, meager salaries with an average income of \$170

(CFA 82,000, or €125) a month provide little incentive for better-qualified teachers (Pearce et al., 2009). Meanwhile, school infrastructure is limited, and of poor quality, textbooks and equipment are often unavailable. These are forerunners' factors of teachers' sitting down strikes and countless demonstrations and demands for better living and working conditions.

However, there is a paucity of research advancing knowledge of teacher job satisfaction and its relation to their job performance, specifically for primary and junior secondary school teachers Mali. That is why this study seeks to fill that gap by exploring, examining, and describing from the teachers' own experiences the factors affecting their job satisfaction and measuring their level of job satisfaction in primary and junior secondary schools in Mali. And it also aims to find out the relationship between the teacher's level of job satisfaction and their job performance in the classroom. This study will also provide insightful and viable recommendations based on the findings on how to increase the level of teachers' job satisfaction and education quality in primary and junior secondary schools in Mali. The study covers the period of ten years, from 2010 to 2021 period in which the government introduced many reforms intending to improve teachers' careers living and working conditions

Purpose of the Study

Following the development of the study about Malian education problems as related to teachers' job satisfaction, one can notice that teachers express discontentment about some aspects of their job. Thus, research must be conducted to find out the intrinsic or extrinsic elements that constitute the factors of this dissatisfaction and establish a set of standards to improve teachers' job satisfaction and eventually end teachers' repetitive strikes and then improve learning outcomes. It is necessary to find out from teachers' experiences what aspects of their job disturb them and the factors which make their job enjoyable. The researcher examined the extent to which intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence teachers' job satisfaction and its

relation to their job performance. Specifically, the importance to which a particular variable yields higher levels of teacher job satisfaction and higher levels of achievement for students

Research Questions

1. The main research question is: What intrinsic and extrinsic factors influence primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction in Mali over the past ten years?
2. Sub-questions:
3. What is the general level of job satisfaction among the primary and junior secondary school teachers in Mali?
4. How does primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction relate to their job performance in Mali?
5. Do urban and rural primary and junior secondary school teachers have the same perception with regard to their job satisfaction in Mali?

Literature review

Related Studies on the Relationship Between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Students' Learning Outcomes

Many researchers and educational practitioners have explored the relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and student learning achievements in the quest for quality education (Abraham et al., 2012; Ashton & Webb, 1986). There is growing evidence that highly competent and effective teachers are indispensable in enhancing student performance. Likewise, there is increasing interest in identifying individual teachers' impact on student achievement (Little et al., 2009). The research discovered that teachers are the most influential factor within schools that policymakers can directly involve to improve student achievement (Rivkin et al., 2005). The more a teacher is committed and satisfied with his job, the better the students' learning outcomes (Ayele, 2014).

Teachers are at the heart of the teaching and learning delivery process and have been pointed out as responsible for students' learning achievements. The change to results-based accountability systems is based on the belief that

objective measurement of student achievement is the best way to measure teachers' effectiveness, and the schools' performance, and connecting results with student performance outcomes motivates better performance (Murphy, 2012). There is enormous interest in developing statistical models that use student scores on standardized tests to assess teachers' effects on student learning.

Are numerous those who established a significant relationship between teachers and students' outcomes or a learning achievement. Improving the teachers' effectiveness would have a considerable impact on the performance of the country's schools, increasing the attainment of children across the education system. Teachers are by far the most extensive resource in schools (Trust, 2011). Wong and Wong (2005) found that teachers directly impact student achievement. Similarly, Hanushek (1992) found, "No other attribute of schools comes close to having this much influence on student achievement. In the same vein, Palardy and Rumberger (2008) concluded that a string of highly effective or ineffective teachers would have an enormous impact on students' learning trajectories throughout grades K-12. Mendro (1998) stipulated that "It is indisputable that teachers have a substantial impact on student achievement, that effects have cumulative contents over time. They further argued that student achievement is at the forefront in the realm of accountability. These researchers maintain that the impact of one bad teacher is reflected in test scores two years later. Slater et al. (2012) noted the strong potential for improving teacher quality, educational standards, and student learning.

Furthermore, Wong and Wong (2005) claimed that the most critical factor, by far, is the teacher. Having a single ineffective teacher can affect student learning for years, and having an ineffective teacher for two years in a row can damage a student's entire academic career. According to Weisberg et al. (2009), a student assigned to an outstanding instructor for a single school year may gain up to a full year's value of supplementary academic growth than a student assigned to a penniless teacher. Ashton and

Webb (1986) further supported the above findings. They contended that satisfaction with teaching as a career is an important policy issue since it is associated with teacher effectiveness, ultimately affecting student achievement.

According to Patrick et al. (2000), teacher enthusiasm leads to more extraordinary student achievement. After analyzing studies in this area, they concluded that it is robust and consistent evidence, from both the laboratory and the classroom, to suggest that students are more likely to be interested, energetic, curious, and excited about learning when a teacher exhibits greater evidence of enthusiasm." Teacher job satisfaction influences job performance which subsequently impacts student achievement during one year with a very effective math teacher; pupils gain 40% more in their learning than they would with a poorly performing math teacher (Aaronson et al., 2007).

Regarding the impact of teachers' morals on students' achievement, Mackenzie (2007) affirmed that when teacher morale is high and the school culture is righteous, teachers are enthusiastic about coming to work and about the job they are doing, this, in turn, impacts student morale and student achievement; though, teachers' low moral can lead to decreased productivity, most notably low student achievement (Mackenzie, 2007). The effects of high-quality education are extensive for pupils from disadvantaged backgrounds, who gain an extra year's worth of learning under very effective teachers compared to poorly performing teachers (Hanushek, 1992). Abel and Swell (1999) concluded that when teachers became emotionally exhausted, they developed negative attitudes toward their students and their jobs, and ultimately few of the educational goals for their students were met. Teachers with a positive sense of self-efficacy believe their work is meaningful and positively impacts student learning (Ashton & Webb, 1986). Ostroff (1992) found positive relationships between teacher satisfaction and indicators of student quality in regards to reading and math skills, discipline problems, and attendance rates. Goddard et al. (2000) reported that collective teacher efficacy

was correlated with student achievement in reading and mathematics.

In contrast, many other views yield that teachers are not exclusively responsible for students learning outcomes. According to Darling-Hammond et al. (1999), it is influenced by many other factors:

- School-related factors, namely: class sizes, curriculum, teaching and learning materials, instructional time, availability of experts and tutors, and learning resources (reading materials, computers, science labs, and more);
- Family and community assistance or challenges;
- Particular student needs and aptitudes, health, and participation;
- Peer influence and achievement;
- previous teachers and schooling, as well as other current teachers;
- Differential summer learning loss, which predominantly influences low-income children; and
- The specific tests used punctuate some kinds of learning and not others and uncommonly assess achievement that is well above or below grades level.

Literate and supportive parents can help their children with homework and secure other learning-related advantages for them. Other children have parents who are incompetent to support their learning intellectually for a variety of reasons. Student test score gains are also impacted by family resources, student health, family mobility, and the influence of neighborhood peers and classmates who may be relatively more advantaged or disadvantaged (Baker et al., 2010).

In summary, there is evidence within the literature that there is a connection between teachers' job satisfaction and students' performance within a classroom. The data suggest that when teacher satisfaction or morale is high, student achievement is elevated as well. Student learning processes and achievement appears to be impacted by teachers' morale.

Research Methodology

The present study adopted a dual epistemological stance combining the philosophical assumption of the positivist and interpretivists traditions. It is anchored on the ontological beliefs that there is an objective reality that is independent of the researcher and accepts the objective view of reality as it appears subjectively, individually, or within a group (Cohen et al., 2007; Muijs, 2004).

On the one hand, this study is embedded in the positivist belief that causes probably determine effects or outcomes). Thus, the problems studied by positivists reflect the need to determine and evaluate the causes that influence results, such as those found in experiments (Creswell, 2009).

Research design

The study adopted the sequential explanatory mixed-methods design. In the sequential explanatory approach, the researcher first begins with a quantitative research phase and explores participants' views.

A survey method was chosen as an appropriate tool to measure the factors influencing primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction in Mali and its relationship to their job performance.

The e-questionnaire choice was motivated by the fact that the researcher could not go to the field of the study because of the Covid-19 pandemic. In this situation, an e-questionnaire was appropriate to collect information from the field of the study. The teacher job satisfaction questionnaire (TJSQ) adapted by Lester (1987), constituted of 66 items, was designated to determine the factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction and to measure Malian primary and junior secondary school teachers' job satisfaction levels.

Sample Size

The minimum sample size was obtained using the single population proportion formula (formulation $n = (Z \alpha / 2)^2 p (1-p/d^2)$ where n = sample size, $Z \alpha / 2$ = statistic for the level of confidence (1.96), p = prevalence of 50% since

there is no similar study in the area and d = margin of error (5%) was taken. Using this calculation 400 sample size was obtained.

A non-respondent rate of 10% was used in order to determine the final sample size. Hence, $400 + 80 = 480$. Therefore, the minimum required sample size for the study was 480. However, a total of 520 teachers participated surpassing the minimum requirement. This sample size perfectly conforms with the Structural Equation Model (SEM), which remains an extensive sample analytical technique. In line with what precedes Hair et al. (2014) further argued that larger samples generally produce more reliable results. The minimum sample size is 100 for models containing five or fewer constructs, each with more than three items (observed variables), 150 for models with seven constructs or less, 300 for models with seven or fewer constructs, and 500 for models with large numbers of constructs, some with lower commonalities, and/or having fewer than three measured items.

Sampling Strategy

The data was collected from two different areas as a representative of the whole country. Bamako (urban) and Kita (rural). This research has used a stratified random sampling technique to choose its participants for its quantitative phase to determine the factors influencing their job satisfaction within these different areas. This stratified random sampling technique has permitted the researcher to divide the target population into sub-groups and obtain a sample population that best represents the whole population. The targeted sample size consisted of male and female teachers teaching in both the first and second cycles. And both generalist and specialist teachers were taken into consideration during the selection process. Thirteen (13) teachers were selected from each cycle in each school.

Data collection procedure

As clearly stipulated above, quantitative and qualitative data were collected sequentially. Quantitative data were collected and analyzed before collecting qualitative data (Creswell & Plano, 2011). In line with this view, qualitative

data help explain the quantitative results. The collection of quantitative data before qualitative data was appropriate for the sequential explanatory mixed-methods design and assisted the two case studies.

Data Analysis

After the data collection, the statistical package of social science (SPSS) software for windows version 25.0. was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics such as mean, median, frequencies, percentages, and standard deviation were computed for the data. In addition to that, inferential analysis was done to determine and make comparisons among the predictor variables. Pearson's correlation coefficients were done to determine the relationship between academic performance and job satisfaction among teachers in the different regions (Bamako and Kita). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and t-test was done to explore the mean difference in job satisfaction between rural and urban settings and other independent variables. Logistic regression analysis was also done to identify the association between predictor and outcome variables. Chi-square analysis was conducted to explore socio-demographic factors associated with job satisfaction among teachers in Mali. To determine the factors associated with job satisfaction among teachers, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was done to ascertain sample adequacy for factor analysis.

Qualitative Part

A case study is incorporated as a qualitative approach within the present study.

At the same time, the researcher selected twenty (20) cases purposively from the quantitative phase of the research project. Therefore, the case study involved Malian primary and junior secondary school teachers from Bamako (rive droite) and Kita (Kita CAP), who were selected from schools with a high level of dissatisfaction in the first quantitative phase.

Results

Quantitative findings

Level of Job Satisfaction among Teachers in the two Regions.

Figure 1. Level of Job Satisfaction in Bamako Region

The Bamako region's overall job satisfaction mean score was 112.75 with a standard deviation of ± 42.85 . The minimum and maximum individual scores were 24 and 213, respectively. The majority of the teachers in the region of Bamako had high job satisfaction, 142 (54.6%).

Figure 2. Level of Job Satisfaction in Kita Region

The low job satisfaction level was higher in the region of Kita (52.5%) than teachers in the region of Bamako (47.3%).

Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction among Teachers in the Two Regions.

Ranked mean score of factors associated with job satisfaction among teachers in Bamako (n=260) and Kita(N=260).

Figure 3. Satisfaction & Dissatisfaction factors in Bamako

The bar chart shows the factors influencing teachers' job satisfaction in the region of Bamako from the least to the highest. From the analysis, interpersonal relationships contributed strongly to the level of satisfaction with an average percentage of 61.8%, followed by responsibility (52.2%) and nature of the work with 45.1%. However, with regards to staff dissatisfaction, salary/pay was the strongest contributor in which 75.9% were dissatisfied and only 19.4% satisfied. This was followed by workload/conditions (71.5%), administrative management system (69.7%), and student success (68%).

The bar chart (figure 4) shows the factors influencing the job satisfaction of teachers in the region of Kita from the least to the highest. From the analysis, like in the region of Bamako, interpersonal relationships contributed strongly to the level of job satisfaction with an average percentage of 64.4%, followed by responsibility (60.3%) and Nature of the work with 55.7%. There is higher satisfaction among these three factors in comparison to the Bamako region. However, with regards to staff dissatisfaction, salary/pay was also the strongest contributor in which 69.3% were dissatisfied and only 28.3% satisfied. This was followed by the administrative management system (62.7%), and Recognition is 61.9% dissatisfaction.

Figure 4. Satisfaction & Dissatisfaction factors for Kita region

Table 1. Correlation Between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Examination Performance of Students in the Kita Region

		Job satisfaction Kita	Pass	Fail
Job satisfaction (Kita)	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
Pass	Pearson Correlation	-0.482		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.158		
Fail	Pearson Correlation	.825	-.694*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003**	0.026	

The analysis revealed that there was a positive correlation between job satisfaction and students' poor performance/fail ($r = .825$, $p = 0.003$) of students in grade 9. Additionally,

there was no significant correlation between job satisfaction and excellent performance/pass of students ($r = -.482$, $p = 0.158$)

Table 2. Correlation Between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Examination Performance of Students in the Bamako Region

		Level of job satisfaction	Pass Grade 9	Fail Grade 9
Level of job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
Pass Grade 9	Pearson Correlation	0.074		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.838		
Fail Grade 9	Pearson Correlation	0.304	.780	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.394	0.008	

The analysis indicated that there was no significant correlation between job satisfaction among teachers and the performance of students.

Correlation Between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Academic Performance in Mali

This question aimed to find out the relationship between teachers' job satisfaction and their job

performance in Mali. To determine the correlation between teachers' job satisfaction and their job performance, we used students' test scores in grades 9 and 6; and a Pearson correlation analysis was conducted. The analysis revealed that job satisfaction was significantly correlated with the performance of teachers in Mali ($r=.295, p<0.001$). It showed that the more satisfied teachers are the better the academic performance of students in Mali.

Table 3. Level of Job Satisfaction Between Teachers in Rural and Urban Areas

	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% CI	
							Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	1.411	0.235	-2.307	498	0.021	-8.392	-15.537	-1.246
Equal variances not assumed			-2.304	490.977	0.022	-8.392	-15.548	-1.235

The analysis revealed that teachers who reside in Bamako (urban) were four times more likely to have high job satisfaction compared to those in Kita (rural) [OR= 4.019, 95% CI: (1.234-13.089), $p=0.021$].

Qualitative findings

Overall Job Satisfaction

Through the use of a semi-structured interview, participants were asked to describe their general level of job satisfaction.

Table 4. Overall Job Satisfaction

Question	Satisfied		Dissatisfied		Total
	Bamako	Kita	Bamako	Kita	
Are you satisfied with your job?	5	2	4	6	17
Total	7		10		17

"Hmmm! To be honest, I am not satisfied with my job as a teacher. I have been teaching for five (5) years, yet still, I couldn't afford my basic needs in life. ' BT01 male teacher

Ufffs humm! I don't know where to start. I would have loved to say I am satisfied with my job as a

teacher because I love teaching, but to be candid, my brother, I am not satisfied with my job at all. BT03 male teacher

Humm! Oooub! First of all, I'm grateful to you for coming up with such an important topic of investigation about teachers' job satisfaction within the Malian context. Genuinely speaking, I am not satisfied with my job as a teacher. ' KT 04 female

"I have always liked teaching since I was in junior school. My love for children gives me satisfaction in this job and my ability to transmit knowledge to the children. I am always happy if I'm with my pupils. Female Teacher BT06

hmmm! I am not satisfied with my profession as a teacher to speak the truth. I entered the teaching field because I couldn't find a job in my field of study, meaning I was left with no option. Female teacher KT07.

The decrease in students' academic achievements is really something which negatively affects my satisfaction simply because teachers are always blamed by the general populace, even by the government, for being the cause of students' low performance.

The content of these speeches confirms the results of the quantitative findings.

Discussion

Results from teachers' responses regarding the intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing their job satisfaction indicate that the majority (51.8%) of the teachers in Mali are not satisfied with their job. This is consistent with Muyobokey (2012) who ascertained that teachers developed a negative attitude towards their teaching careers in Rwanda. Consistent with Chen (2010), who determined that middle school teachers in Jinzhou City in China were prone to be dissatisfied with their job in general. The factors associated with job satisfaction are the interpersonal relationship ($M=16.99$), the nature of work ($\text{mean}=15.33$), and the responsibility ($\text{mean}=6.46$). The elements that account for dissatisfaction are working conditions ($M=15.52$), salary ($M=13.91$), recognition ($M=3.195$), students' success ($M=12.64$), administrative management system ($M=19.94$), professional development ($M=5.43$), advancement and promotion ($M=7.96$), and recognition ($M=7.7$).

These findings are in line with Raymond (2018) who stated that teachers are dissatisfied with district policies and the administration in Massachusetts (USA). These findings are in perfect harmony with the results by Evan and Yuan (2018), as they noted that teachers in low- and Middle-income countries struggle with difficult living and working condition. Congruent with Usop et al. (2013) who revealed that teachers are not satisfied with their salaries in Cotabato District.

This present study indicates a positive correlation between job satisfaction and students' poor performance ($r=0.673$, $p=0.033$). These findings are in line with Kaditong et al. (2017), who ascertained a moderate correlation between teaching performance and job satisfaction. Genelyn et al. (2019) suggested that job satisfaction affects students' performance; and that educational development is not plausible without improving these two factors.

The study showed that teachers in urban areas are more satisfied with their job than teachers in rural areas. The study findings are incoherent with (Wani et al's., 2013) findings. They revealed that rural higher secondary school teachers are more satisfied than urban higher secondary school teachers.

Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are made: teachers job satisfaction and work performance are very crucial for the improvement of the quality of education in every educational system around the world. When Teachers are satisfied with their job, and their social and professional (opportunity for professional development, in-service training, attractive salaries, welfare support services) needs are taken into account at the height of the wish they become motivated, and productive. Teacher job satisfaction and work performance would further be enhanced when teachers are offered recognition on the job, benefit a better administrative management system, attractive salary. It is worth emphasizing that teacher job satisfaction and work performance are essential concept, which require much attention and commitment by the school stakeholders in order to reach the expected goals of the education system.

Based on the conclusion, education practitioners should consider the following points revealed by the study findings. 1) Therefore, there is a need to digitalize the administration file management system making the processing of files fluid so that teachers can get their files at the expected time. 2) there is a need to strengthen the system to promote based on experience and performance. 3) School leaders should establish equity and justice between teachers in the work environment regardless of political or other related backgrounds. 4) education policymakers should reduce the class size considerably because small class sizes allow all the students to talk and participate in the teaching activities and improve learning quality. 5) Education policymakers should provide adequate teaching and learning materials. 6) The government should review the

teachers' salary policy to give a satisfactory salary to teachers equal to the salary of other civil servants of the country. 7) The school administration should initiate more workshops and training activities for teachers. 8) the school authorities should implement a team recognition program in which awards are assigned based on the whole team's effort.

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